

EVALUATION OF FERTILITY RESPONSE IN MODIFIED OVSYNCH PROTOCOL TREATED POSTPARTUM ANESTRUS COWS

Pushendra Maravi^{1*}, Nitin Kumar Bajaj¹, Pooja Dawar¹, Renuka Mishra¹, Shashank Vishvakarma¹, Pankaj Kumar Umar¹, Jyoti¹ and Aditya Mishra¹

¹College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, NDVSU, Jabalpur, (M.P.)-482001, India.

ABSTRACT

The present study was planned to evaluate the comparative efficacy of modified Ovsynch protocols in postpartum anestrus cows. A total of 135 postpartum cows reared under field conditions in Jabalpur (M.P.) were surveyed during the study. The cows with the history of not showing signs of oestrus for 60 days or more postpartum were considered to be suffering from postpartum anestrus. These cows were per rectally examined twice at 10 days apart to confirm ovarian activity. Twenty Four postpartum anestrus cows were randomly selected from the cows found positive for anestrus. These animals were again randomly divided into 4 groups (n=6 animal/group) and were dewormed. Group I, II and III animals were treated with CIDR plus Ovsynch, Ovsynch combined with reused autoclaved CIDR and Vit. E and Selenium protocol and Ovsynch along with mifepristone and hCG protocol, respectively. However, control group (Group IV) animals were not given any treatment. All treatment group animals were bred by fixed time artificial insemination while control animals were bred on observed oestrus by artificial insemination. Serum progesterone (ng/ml) levels and biochemical parameters (total protein, total cholesterol, calcium, phosphorus and magnesium) were also estimated on day 0 and day 21 post AI. Pregnancy diagnosis was done by per rectal examination 60 days post insemination to assess the fertility rate in terms of conception rate. Significant ($p < 0.05$) increase was observed in mean serum progesterone (P_4) concentration (ng/ml) between day 0 and day 21 post AI in all the treatment groups and control group. No significant variation was observed in biochemical parameters on day 0 and day 21 post AI. The conception rate was highest in Ovsynch along with mifepristone and hCG protocol (83.33%). Thus, it can be concluded that Ovsynch along with mifepristone and hCG protocol provides better fertility with maximum conception rate. Reused CIDR have residual progesterone and incorporating them in Ovsynch protocol also have good oestrus induction and conception rate.

Keywords: Postpartum anestrus cows, fertility response, Serum progesterone, Ovsynch protocol, Mifeprestone

INTRODUCTION

Postpartum anestrus refers to a condition where cows have not been observed or reported in oestrus for several weeks after calving, often to the end of the voluntary waiting period, in dairy cattle. While a

short period of ovarian inactivity during the immediate postpartum period is normal, extended anestrus in non-suckled cattle such as dairy cows could have negative ramifications on the timely reestablishment of pregnancy (Roche *et al.*, 1992). It has been proposed that anestrus occurs more frequently in high-yielding cows. Anestrus may arise from an increased allocation of energy towards milk production, which postpones the restart of follicular activity. In order to break or abbreviate postpartum anestrus and restore the hormonal and metabolic balance of the cow, numerous dietary and hormonal techniques have been devised (Savalia *et al.*, 2014). Only animals with high nutritional status can benefit from hormonal therapy to increase the effectiveness of their reproductive processes when they are in anestrus. A variety of hormones, including gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), prostaglandins linked to fixed-time artificial insemination (FTAI), progesterone (CIDR, Crestar), pregnant mare serum gonadotropin (PMSG), and gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), have been used in oestrus induction protocols with varying degrees of success in treating anestrus (Kumar *et al.*, 2014). A new follicular wave appears in the CIDR plus Ovsynch protocol when the insertion of CIDR results in an abrupt surge in progesterone and a subsequent drop in pituitary LH output. This produces atresia of all the big follicles present at the ovaries (Martinez-Ros and Gonzalez-Bulnes, 2019). Progesterone in any form acts by maintaining negative feedback over the hypothalamus-pituitary axis and restricting the release of gonadotrophins, that is, follicle-stimulating hormone and luteinizing hormone, although the synthesis of gonadotropin still remains to continue. When the negative feedback is withdrawn, there is a reflex release of these gonadotrophins resulting in the induction of oestrus within 2-5 days of progesterone removal (Barlie, 2012). Keeping this in view, the present study was planned to evaluate the comparative efficacy of modified Ovsynch protocols in postpartum anestrus cows.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present research work was carried out in the Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Jabalpur (M.P.) and different villages of Jabalpur (M.P.), India.

Selection of animal

A total of 135 postpartum cows (BCS >2.5) reared under field conditions in different villages of Jabalpur (M.P.) were surveyed during the study period of six months. The calving and breeding history of animals provided by the dairy owners was recorded during the survey and per-rectal examination (cervix, uterus and ovary) was also done to evaluate the genital status of the animals. The cows with the history of not showing signs of oestrus for 60 days or more postpartum were considered to be suffering from postpartum anestrus. These cows were per rectally examined twice at 10 days apart to confirm ovarian activity. Twenty four postpartum anestrus cows (body condition score >2.5) were randomly selected from the cows found positive for anestrus. These animals were randomly divided into four groups *i.e.* three treatment group and one untreated

control group (n=06 animals/group) and were dewormed. The animals of treatment groups were subjected to various oestrus induction protocols after 07 days of deworming as follows:

Table 01: Treatment protocols for different groups

S. No.	Groups(n=06/group)	Treatmentregimen	Schedule
1	I (CIDR + Ovsynch protocol)	Inj.GnRH (Buserelin acetate, 20 µg,I/M)+CIDR Implant	Day 0
		Inj.PGF _{2α} (Cloprostenol,500 µg, I/M)	Day 07
		Removal of CIDR Implant	Day 08
		Inj.GnRH (Buserelin acetate, 10 µg,I/M)	Day 09
		FTAI	10 Day (24hrs. After second GnRH injection)
2	II (Reused autoclaved CIDR + Ovsynch + Inj.VitaminE&Selenium protocol)	Inj.GnRH(Buserelin acetate, 20 µg,I/M)+ Reused autoclaved Implant + Inj. Vitamin E& Selenium(1ml/50kg)	Day0
		Inj.PGF _{2α} (Cloprostenol, 500 µg, I/M)+ Inj.VitaminE&Selenium(1ml/50kg)	Day07
		RemovalofCIDRimplant	Day08
		Inj.GnRH(Buserelin acetate, 10 µg,I/M)	Day09
		FTAI	10 Day (24hrs aftersecond GnRHinjection)

3	III Ovsynch + Mifepristone +hCG protocol)	Inj.GnRH(Buserelin acetate, 20µg,I/M)	Day0
		Inj.PGF _{2α} (Cloprostenol,500µg, I/M)	Day07
		Inj.GnRH(Buserelin acetate, 10µg,I/M) + Tab. Mifepristone (1mg/kg)10-15min afterTab. CuSO ₄ (1500 mg)orally	Day09
		FTAI	10 Day (24hrs. after second GnRHinjection)
		Inj.hCG (2000IU,I/M)	Day15
4	V Control	No treatment	AI on oestrus

FTAI- Fixed time artificial insemination, Day 0- Start of experiment

Collection of Blood

Five millilitre blood was collected aseptically from the external jugular vein from all the experimental cattle on day 0 of treatment and day 21 post AI. Serum was separated at 1500 rpm for 30 minutes and stored in labelled vials in deep freezer at -20°C till estimation of biochemical parameters and progesterone estimation.

Serum Progesterone Assay

Serum progesterone concentration (ng/ml) was estimated on the day of initiation of treatment (0 day) and day 21 post AI for confirming the results obtained on gynaeco-clinical examination. The results of progesterone assay were correlated with the fertility response to treatment in terms of conception rates. The quantitative determination of progesterone concentration in plasma was done by ELISA using commercial kit manufactured by Alkor Bio Inc., Russia.

Estimation of Biochemical Parameters in Serum Samples

The levels of minerals, *viz.* calcium, phosphorus, magnesium in serum were determined on day 0 (day of initiation of treatment) and day 21 post AI by auto analyzer. Serum calcium, phosphorus, cholesterol and total protein were analysed in semi auto analyser by using commercial kit

manufactured by Erba Manheim, Transasia biochemical (India) Pvt. Ltd. Serum magnesium was analysed on semi auto analyser by using commercial kit manufactured by LAB-CARE diagnostics (India) Pvt. Ltd.

Conception Rate

Pregnancy diagnosis was done by per rectal examination on 60 days post artificial insemination to determine the conception rate.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analysed on R platform (R Core Team, 2018) using “dplyr” library. Data from different experiments were presented as Mean \pm SE. The pair-wise comparison of means was carried out using Fisher’s multiple comparison test as per standard statistical method described by Snedecor and Cochran (1994). The results of conception rates were expressed in percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mean Serum Progesterone Concentration (ng/ml)

Serum progesterone concentration is specifically related with CL function and fertility of the cows. The progesterone concentration is responsible for stimulation of cyclicity, follicular development and also for continuation of pregnancy. In normal cyclic cow, serum progesterone level is expected to be high during dioestrus stage and subsequently should reduce during oestrus stage. Anestrus cows carry irregular levels of progesterone which create uncertainty in exhibition of next oestrus and the stage continues for months together unless disrupted by endogenous or exogenous hormones. Mean serum progesterone (P₄) concentration (ng/ml) was studied in anestrus cows on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI in different treatment groups and the results are presented in table 02.

Table 02: Mean serum progesterone (P₄) concentration (ng/ml) in control and different treatment groups

Group (n=06/group)	Day 0	Day 21 post AI
I	1.97 ^b \pm 0.27	4.29 ^a \pm 0.38
II	2.09 ^b \pm 0.16	4.48 ^a \pm 0.29
III	2.05 ^b \pm 0.45	4.73 ^a \pm 0.35

IV	1.99 ^b ±0.15	3.51 ^a ±0.56
----	-------------------------	-------------------------

Mean values bearing different superscripts (a,b) in a row differ significantly ($p < 0.05$)

Significant ($p < 0.05$) increase was observed in mean serum progesterone (P_4) concentration (ng/ml) between day 0 and day 21 post AI in all the treatment groups and control group.

The variation in mean serum progesterone (P_4) concentration (ng/ml) between different groups on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

Niazet *al.* (2022) in their study on postpartum cross bred cattle using Ovsynch and progesterone implants reported that mean serum progesterone (P_4) concentration (ng/ml) in control and different treatment groups on day 0 ranged from 1.36 ± 0.58 to 3.11 ± 0.85 and on day 21 post AI from 4.00 ± 1.76 to 11.31 ± 4.46 . They also reported that the increase in mean serum progesterone (P_4) concentration (ng/ml) from days 0 to 21 post- insemination was non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

The significant ($p > 0.05$) increase in mean serum progesterone (P_4) concentration (ng/ml) from days 0 to 21 post- insemination is clearly inflicted in form of conception rate in control and different treatment groups. Similarly, it was reported that higher plasma P_4 in pregnant than non-pregnant cows indicate luteal insufficiency or anovulation in non-pregnant animals. The pregnancy rate in cows was positively associated with higher progesterone concentration in the luteal phase of the cycle preceding AI (Bhoraniyaet *al.*, 2012 and Dhamiet *al.*, 2019).

Serum Biochemical Parameters

Minerals affect various physiological activities as they function as cofactors, activators of enzymes, or stabilizers of secondary molecular structure. Minerals are absorbed only mainly through the small intestine. A deficiency of mineral elements like Ca, P, Mg, etc. is associated with subnormal fertility, decreased ovarian activity, irregular oestrus and anestrus condition. The imbalance of minerals leads to anestrus and inactive ovaries associated with increased estrogen production by ovarian follicles. Cows having a deficiency of minerals are known to exhibit delayed sexual maturity and prolonged postpartum anestrus period (Thakur, 2018). The mean serum profiles of various minerals found at day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI in different group animals (Ovsynch combined with CIDR group, Ovsynch combined with reused autoclaved CIDR and Vit. E and Selenium group, Ovsynch along with mifepristone and hCG group, control group) and control groups are presented in tables 03 to 07.

Mean Serum Calcium Concentration

Calcium appears to affect reproduction in animals indirectly. It influences the animal's ability to use other trace elements thus leading to a disruption of reproductive efficiency. The results of mean serum calcium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI observed in different treatment groups are summarized in table 03.

Table 03: Mean serum calcium concentration (mg/dl) in control and different treatment groups

Group (n=06/group)	Day 0	Day 21 post AI
I	10.13±0.82	9.89±0.31
II	10.20±0.51	10.02±0.82
III	10.30±0.78	10.10±0.83
IV	9.16±0.28	8.91±0.34

Non-significant ($p>0.05$) decrease in serum mean calcium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within group I, II, III and IV. Non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in mean serum calcium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed between group I, II, III and IV.

Similar to finding of present study, Niazet *al.* (2022) in their study on induction of oestrus in postpartum anestrus crossbred cattle also reported non-significant variation in mean serum calcium levels form day 0 and day 21 post AI (6.02±0.54 and 8.06±1.14). The findings of the present study are in corroboration with the findings of Virmaniet *al.* (2011) who observed mean serum calcium (mg/dl) concentration in CIDR and Ovsynch group on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was 7.50±1.21 and 8.54±0.78 and 7.18±1.41 and 9.74±1.47, respectively.

Kumar *et al.* (2020) observed serum mean calcium (mg/dl) concentration in the Ovsynch plus mineral mixture group on day pre-treatment and post-treatment were 7.74±0.06 and 9.49±0.05, respectively.

Mean Serum Phosphorus Concentration

Phosphorus deficiency affects pituitary and ovarian hormone levels, which in turn leads to abnormalities in the regular cycle of reproduction. The results of mean serum phosphorus (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI observed in different treatment groups are summarized in table 04.

Table 04: Mean serum phosphorus concentration (mg/dl) in control and different treatment groups

Group (n=06/group)	Day 0	Day 21 post AI
I	5.96±0.31	5.69±0.37
II	5.87±0.47	5.57±0.43
III	5.96±0.29	5.75±0.46
IV	5.78±0.32	5.47±0.36

Non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in mean serum phosphorus (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within the group I, II, III and IV. Non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in mean serum phosphorus (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed between groups I, II, III and IV.

The findings of the present study are similar to the findings of Virmaniet *al.* (2011) who observed mean serum phosphorus (mg/dl) concentration in CIDR and Ovsynch group on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was 4.28 ± 0.51 and 5.89 ± 0.44 and 4.15 ± 0.66 and 4.98 ± 0.55 , respectively. They also reported non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in mean serum phosphorus (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within the groups.

The findings of Niazet *al.* (2022) are also similar to findings of present study as they observed mean serum phosphorus (mg/dl) concentration in Ovsynch group on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI were 4.99 ± 0.69 and 4.74 ± 0.58 , respectively.

Mean Serum Magnesium Concentration

Magnesium usually does not have direct impact on the reproductive status of animals, since in body it remains in almost antagonistic relation with calcium and any disturbance in Ca-P-Mg homeostasis can impart some influence on reproduction. Moreover reduced reproductive efficiency encountered loss of appetite due to magnesium deficiency (Kumar, 2003). The results of mean serum magnesium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI observed in different treatment groups are summarized in table 05.

Table 05: Mean serum magnesium concentration (mg/dl) in control and different treatment groups

Group (n=06/group)	Day 0	Day 21 post AI
I	2.05±0.20	2.06±0.18
II	1.86±0.30	2.03±0.30
III	1.98±0.19	2.23±0.12
IV	2.06 ^a ±0.19	1.90 ^b ±0.23

Non-significant variation in serum mean magnesium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed between groups I, II III and IV. Non-significant variation ($p>0.05$) in mean serum magnesium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within groups I, II and III while significant ($p<0.05$) variation in mean serum magnesium (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within the group IV. The findings of the present study are comparable with the findings of Anushmaet *al.* (2020) who observed serum mean magnesium (mg/dl) concentration in postpartum anestrus and normal cyclic animals as 2.71 ± 0.233 and 2.82 ± 0.093 , respectively.

Mean serum total protein concentration

Protein is one of the most important nutrients for dairy cow reproduction and should be prioritised. Protein deficiency has been linked to poor reproductive performance (Bindariet *al.*, 2013). The results of mean serum total protein (g/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI observed in different treatment groups are summarized in table 06.

Table 06: Mean serum total protein concentration (g/dl) in control and different treatment groups

Group (n=06/group)	Day 0	Day 21 post AI
I	6.61±0.90	7.79±0.61
II	6.77±0.58	7.29±0.41
III	7.20±0.70	8.48±0.76
IV	7.69±1.10	7.78±0.81

Non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in serum mean total protein (g/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within groups I, II, III and IV. Non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in mean serum total protein (g/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed between groups I, II, III and IV.

The findings of the present study are similar to the findings of Virmaniet al. (2011) who observed mean serum total protein (g/dl) concentration in CIDR group on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was 6.52±0.57 and 7.77±0.54, respectively. In the Ovsynch group, serum mean total protein (g/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was 6.98±0.57 and 7.75±0.48, respectively.

The findings of the present study are comparable with the findings of Anushmaet al. (2020) who observed serum mean total protein (g/dl) concentration in postpartum anestrus and normal cyclic animals were 6.72±0.165 and 6.75±0.109, respectively.

Similarly, Agrawal et al. (2015) reported higher serum protein concentration in cyclic than anestrus animals (8.20±1.09 g/dl vs 6.58±1.04 g/dl). However, Mahouret al. (2011) reported higher serum total protein in anestrus cows against induced oestrus cows (7.29±0.31 gm/dl vs 6.36±0.48 gm/dl). Whereas, Bhoraniyaet al. (2012) observed lower total protein level in anestrus cows than in normal cyclic cows (5.89±0.23 vs and 6.20±0.20 gm/dl).

Mean Serum Cholesterol Concentration

The cholesterol being precursor of steroid and cholesterol profile denote nutritional status of animals and are related with their fertility. The results of mean serum cholesterol (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI observed in different treatment groups are summarized in table 07.

Table 07: Mean serum cholesterol concentration (mg/dl) in control and different treatment groups

Group (n=06/group)	Day 0	Day 21 days AI
I	158.27±16.78	194.86±27.13
II	181.69±0.73	229.32±12.36
III	147.33±1.80	197.06±20.06
IV	155.45 ^b ±13.64	212.01 ^a ±12.91

Non-significant ($p>0.05$) increase in serum mean cholesterol (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within the group I, II, III while a significant ($p<0.05$) increase in serum mean cholesterol (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed within-group IV. Non-significant ($p>0.05$) variation in serum mean cholesterol (mg/dl) concentration on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was observed between group I, II, III and IV.

The findings of the present study are comparable with the findings of Anushma *et al.* (2020) who observed mean serum cholesterol (mg/dl) concentration in postpartum anestrus and normal cyclic animals were 162.63±9.78 and 197.64±10.87, respectively.

Virmaniet *et al.* (2011) observed mean serum cholesterol (mg/dl) concentration in CIDR and Ovsynch group on day 0 of the treatment and day 21 post AI was 218.36±38.52 and 156.93±18.23 and 181.38±16.01 and 149.86±26.01, respectively. The mean value of cholesterol in post-partum anestrus group (162.63±9.78) was significantly lower than the normal cyclic group (253.44±20.66) which is in concurrence with the findings of Akhtar *et al.* (2010).

Conception rate

Fertility rates in postpartum anestrus cows treated with different oestrus induction protocols were recorded in terms of conception rates. The conception rates obtained in postpartum anestrus cattle after artificial insemination are depicted in table 08.

Table 08: Conception rates in control and different treatment groups in postpartum anestrus cows

Groups (N=06/Group)	Conception rate (per cent)
I	50.00 (3)
II	66.67 (4)
III	83.33 (5)
IV (Control)	16.66 (1)

Figures in parenthesis indicate number of animals

Conception rate (50.00%) observed in this study in CIDR + Ovsynch group animals might be due to the synchrony between luteolysis, ovulation and TAI and the supplementation of progesterone through CIDR (Stevenson *et al.*, 2006). The other reason of conception with this protocol might be due to increased concentrations of estradiol -17 beta in cows treated previously with progesterone that caused the release of more LH after GnRH resulting in increased ovulatory response and in turn conception rates (Thompson *et al.*, 1999). In addition, supplementation of progesterone with GnRH significantly reduce the dominant follicle size at the time of PGF_{2α} treatment and improve fertility, apparently due to the reduced occurrence of the persistence of follicles (Martinez *et al.*, 2002). Furthermore, serum progesterone concentration in CIDR-treated cows remained elevated for seven days (to the time of CIDR removal) might have increased the conception rate since higher blood progesterone concentration during the luteal phase preceding insemination increase conception rates in dairy cows (Folman *et al.*, 1990).

In the present study conception rate in Ovsynch combined with reused autoclaved CIDR and Vit. E & Se protocol (group II) was 66.67 per cent. Lower conception rates have been observed by El-Tarabany (2016) as conception rates per AI at day 28 using the New-CIDRsynch and Used-CIDRsynch regimens as 35.9% and 29.2%, respectively. But these rates were significantly greater than those in plain Ovsynch group animals. Similarly, Abdallah and El-Rahim (2014) observed lower pregnancy rates at day 30 and 70 after New-CIDRsynch (36.1% and 30.5%) and Reused-CIDRsynch (36.4% and 31.8%) tended to be higher than after Ovsynch alone regimen (27.7% and 25.2%). Solorzano *et al.* (2003) observed 69 per cent pregnancy in used CIDR-treated females. Arechiga *et al.* (1998) observed that addition of vitamin E and selenium increases the pregnancy rate at the first and second service (45.4 Vs 69.8%) and reduced services per conception. Vitamin-E and Selenium play important role in improving the quality of oocytes, promoting FSH & LH release, influence uterine involution, postpartum ovarian activity and improving germinal layer of uterus. Selenium being component of enzyme glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), in combination with vitamin E serves as a biological antioxidant to maintain cellular integrity (Razzaque *et al.*,

2009). The action of vitamin E and selenium is also synergistic. Therefore, supplementation of vitamin E and selenium which acts as an antioxidant resulted into higher conception rate and decrease in service per conception (Khan *et al.*, 2014). The association of vitamin E to the oestrus synchronization protocol with the use of progesterone is beneficial for the obtainment of good reproductive results (Zanella *et al.*, 2010).

In the present study, conception rate in Ovsynch along with mifepristone and hCG protocol (group III) was 66.67 per cent. Abulaiti *et al.* (2022) observed 45.80 per cent of pregnancy in GPGMH (GPG-Mifepristone-hCG) protocol. Mifepristone having anti-progestogenic mechanism might have reduced progesterone concentration. High progesterone concentrations possibly inhibit the onset of LH surge following the second GnRH, leading to the formation of follicular cysts (Khan *et al.*, 2011).

CONCLUSION

Ovsynch along with mifepristone and hCG protocol provides better fertility with maximum conception rate. Reused CIDR have residual progesterone and incorporating them in Ovsynch protocol also have good conception rate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors are thankful to Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, NDVSU, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India for providing the financial support to the research work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Abdallah, H. and El-Rahim, A.A. (2014). Efficiency of previously used CIDR stored for a prolonged period. *Advances in Animal and Veterinary Sciences*, **2**(9): 508-515.
- Abulaiti, A., Naseer, Z., Ahmed, Z., Wang, D., Hua, G. and Yang, L. (2022). Effect of different synchronization regimens on reproductive variables of crossbred (swamp× riverine) nulliparous and multiparous buffaloes during peak and low breeding seasons. *Animals*, **12**(4): 415.
- Agrawal, J., Saxena, A. and Singh, V. (2015). Study on metabolic profile of repeat breeder, postpartum anestrus and normal cyclic Sahiwal cows. *Indian Journal of Animal Reproduction*, **36**(1): 53-55.
- Akhtar, M.S., Farooq, A.A. and Mushtaq, M. (2010). Biochemical and hormonal profile in anestrus Nili Ravi buffaloes. *Indian Veterinary Journal*, **87**: 603-604.
- Anushma, Kumar, P., Singh, M. and Sharma, A. (2020). Hematobiochemical and Mineral Profile Evaluation in Post-partum Anestrus cows. *Intas Polivet*, **21**(2): 374-376.

- Arechiga, C.F., Vazquez-Flores, S., Ortiz, O., Hernandez-Ceron, J., Porras, A., McDowell, L.R. and Hansen, P.J. (1998). Effect of injection of β -carotene or vitamin E and selenium on fertility of lactating dairy cows. *Theriogenology*, **50**(1): 65-76.
- Barile, V.L. (2012). Technologies related with the artificial insemination in buffalo. *Journal of Buffalo Science*, **1**(2): 139-146.
- Bindari, Y.R., Shrestha, S., Shrestha, N. and Gaire, T.N. (2013). Effects of nutrition on reproduction-A review. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, **4**(1): 421-429.
- Bhoraniya, H.L., Dharni, A.J., Naikoo, M., Parmar, B.C. and Sarvaiya, N.P. (2012). Effect of estrus synchronization protocols on plasma progesterone profile and fertility in postpartum anestrous Kankrej cows. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, **44**(6): 1191-1197.
- Dharni, A.J., Patel, J.A., Hadiya, K.K., Parmar, S.C. and Chaudhari, D.V. (2019). Nutritional infertility and ameliorative measures in dairy animals of middle Gujarat. *The Indian Journal of Veterinary Sciences and Biotechnology*, **14**(3): 5-9.
- El-Tarabany, M.S. (2016). The efficiency of new CIDR and once-used CIDR to synchronize ovulation in primiparous and multiparous Holstein cows. *Animal Reproduction Science*, **173**: 29-34.
- Folman, Y., Kaim, M., Herz, Z. and Rosenberg, M. (1990). Comparison of methods for the synchronization of estrous cycles in dairy cows. 2. Effects of progesterone and parity on conception. *Journal of Dairy Science*, **73**(10): 2817-2825.
- Khan, F.A., Das, G.K., Pande, M., Pathak, M.K. and Sarkar, M. (2011). Biochemical and hormonal composition of follicular cysts in water buffalo (*Bubalus bubalis*). *Animal Reproduction Science*, **124**(1-2): 61-64.
- Khan, H.M., Bhakat, M., Mohanty, T.K. and Pathbanda, T.K. (2014). Influence of vitamin E, macro and micro minerals on reproductive performance of cattle and buffalo-a review. *Agricultural Reviews*, **35**(2): 113-121.
- Kumar, S. (2003). Management of infertility due to mineral deficiency in dairy animals. *Proceedings of ICAR summer school on "Advance diagnostic techniques and therapeutic approaches to metabolic and deficiency diseases in dairy animals"*. Held at IVRI, Izatnagar, 128-137.
- Kumar, J., Srivastava, S., Kumar, R., Mohan, G. and Chaudhry, V. (2020). Effect of *Janova*, *Sepia* and Ovsynch protocol on blood biochemical profile and fertility in postpartum anestrous cows. *Indian Journal of Animal Research*, **56**(9): 1077-1083.
- Kumar, P.R., Singh, S.K., Kharche, S.D., Govindaraju, C.S., Behera, B.K., Shukla, S.N., Kumar, H. and Agarwal, S.K. (2014). Anestrus in cattle and buffalo: Indian perspective. *Advances in Animal and Veterinary Sciences*, **2**(3): 124-138.
- Mahour, S.S., Nema, S.P., Shukla, S.P., Shrivastava, N. and Mehta, H.K. (2011). Biochemical profile of postpartum anestrous and induced estrus crossbred cows. *Indian Journal of Field Veterinarians*, **6**(3): 53-55.

- Martinez, M.F., Kastelic, J.P., Adams, G.P., Cook, B., Olson, W.O. and Mapletoft, R.J. (2002). The use of progestins in regimens for fixed-time artificial insemination in beef cattle. *Theriogenology*, **57**(3): 1049-1059
- Martinez-Ros, P. and Gonzalez-Bulnes, A. (2019). Efficiency of CIDR-based protocols including GnRH instead of eCG for estrus synchronization in sheep. *Animals*, **9**(4): 146.
- Niaz, S., Naiko, M., Islam, R., Lone, F.A. and Khan, A.A. (2022). Induction of Estrus in Postpartum Anestrus Crossbred Cattle. *Indian Journal of Veterinary Sciences & Biotechnology*, **18**(4): 21-25.
- R Core Team. (2018). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. Vienna: R Foundation for statistical computing.
- Razzaque, W.A.A., Sahatpura, S.K. and Sudershan, K. (2009). Behavioural changes during supraovulatory oestrus with FSH-P in polyvinylpyrrolidone in cross bred cows. *Indian Journal of Dairy Science*, **60**(4): 307.
- Roche, J.F., Crowe, M.A. and Boland, M.P. (1992). Postpartum anestrus in dairy and beef cows. *Animal Reproduction Science*, **28**(1-4): 371-378.
- Savalia, K.K., Dharni, A.J., Hadiya, K.K., Patel, K.R. and Sarvaiya, N.P. (2014). Influence of controlled breeding techniques on fertility and plasma progesterone, protein and cholesterol profile in true anestrus and repeat breeding buffaloes. *Veterinary World*, **7**(9): 727-732.
- Snedecor, G.W. and Cochran, W.G. (1994). *Statistical Methods*, 8th Edn., Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., New Delhi, pp 312-317.
- Solorzano, C.W., Mendoza, J.H., Oden, J. and Romo, S. (2003). Pregnancy rates after estrus synchronization treatment with new and reused CIDR-b devices. *Reproduction, Fertility and Development*, **16**(2): 214.
- Stevenson, J.S., Pursley, J.R., Garverick, H.A., Fricke, P.M., Kesler, D.J., Ottobre, J.S. and Wiltbank, M.C. (2006). Treatment of cycling and noncycling lactating dairy cows with progesterone during Ovsynch. *Journal of Dairy Science*, **89**(7): 2567-2578.
- Thakur, R.V. (2018). Comparative efficacy of different synchronization protocols for oestrus induction in postpartum anestrus cows. M.V.Sc. thesis (Gynaecology and Obstetrics), Nanajideshmukh veterinary science university, Jabalpur.
- Thompson, K.E., Stevenson, J.S., Lamb, G.S., Grieger, D.M. and Loest, C.A. (1999). Follicular, hormonal and pregnancy responses of early postpartum suckled beef cows to GnRH, norgestomet and prostaglandin F2a. *Journal of Animal Science*, **77**: 1823-1832.
- Virmani, M., Malik, R.K., Singh, P. and Dalal, S.S. (2011). Studies on blood biochemical and mineral profiles with the treatment of acyclicity in post-partum anestrus sahiwal cows. *Haryana Veterinarian*, **50**(12): 77-79.
- Zanella, R., Bondan, C., Soares, J.C.M., Zanella, E.L. and Lima, M.R.D. (2010). Use of antioxidants to improve the pregnancy rate in beef cattle submitted to a synchronization protocol with progesterone (P4). *Ciencia Animal Brasileira*, **11**: 477-481.